

Studies in Copper(II) Complexes : Part II. Diisothiocyanato—, Dinitro- and Diazidomono (α, α' -Dipyridyl/*o*-Phenanthroline) Copper (II) Complexes

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Several copper(II) complexes of empirical composition $[\text{Cu}(\text{AA})(\text{X})_2]$ (where $(\text{AA}) = \alpha, \alpha'$ -dipyridyl/*o*-phenanthroline / 5-nitro-*o*-phenanthroline and $\text{X} = \text{NCS}, \text{NO}_2$ or N_3) have been isolated in pure, crystalline forms. These complexes are all green to dark green in colour and are insoluble in water and many common organic solvents. They all record paramagnetic moments ~ 1.7 — 1.9 B. M. Representative infrared spectral studies indicate nitrogen co-ordination for both of the NCS- and NO_2 -complexes. Evidence of terminal and of weakly bridging isothiocyanate and nitrite are also available. Reflectance spectra and solution spectra in dimethylsulfoxide suggest distorted octahedral structures at least in solution phase.

While working on the copper (II) mixed chelates of the type $[\text{Cu}(\text{AA})(\text{BigH})]\text{X}_2$ (where $(\text{AA}) = \text{o-phenanthroline} / \alpha, \alpha'$ -dipyridyl/5-nitro-*o*-phenanthroline; $\text{BigH} = \text{biguanide}$ or subst. biguanide and $\text{X} = \text{Cl}, \text{Br}$ or I), it was observed¹ that ammonium thiocyanate brought about complete decomposition of the mixed chelate systems and resulted in the formation of intense green, $[\text{Cu}(\text{AA})(\text{NCS})_2]$. This paper presents an investigation of reactions with thiocyanate, azide and nitrite ions.

Mono (α, α' -dipyridyl)—and mono (*o*-phenanthroline) copper (II) complexes containing thiocyanate ion seem to have been mentioned in a preliminary communication², although no details are yet available. A recent study on some transition metals thiocyanato (*o*-phenanthroline) mixed ligand complexes³ only indicates failure in isolating the desired monocomplexes containing two thiocyanato groups in a reasonably pure state.** We describe two simple procedures for such syntheses : (1) addition of excess thiocyanate, nitrite or azide to an aqueous solution of the mixed chelates $[\text{Cu}(\text{AA})(\text{BigH})\text{X}_2]$ results in the precipitation of complexes of the type $[\text{Cu}(\text{AA})(\text{X})_2]$; (2) addition of thiocyanate, nitrite or azide to an aqueous alcoholic solution of CuCl_2 and the heterocyclic ligands in 1:1 proportion also provides the same complexes.

The complexes in general are highly insoluble in water and common organic solvents, such as chloroform, benzene, dioxane, etc. but are readily soluble in dimethylsulfoxide to a green or yellowish green colour. The extreme water-insolubility $[\text{Cu}(\text{AA})(\text{NCS})_2]$ (where $\text{AA} = \alpha, \alpha'$ -dipyridyl/*o*-phenanthroline) has offered us an excellent procedure for gravimetric estimation of the co-ordinated α, α' -dipyridyl or *o*-phenanthroline in our mixed chelate complexes.

Complex $[\text{Cu}(\text{AA})(\text{NCS})_2]$ ($\text{AA} = \alpha, \alpha'$ -dipyridyl): The infra-red spectra has been run as a nujol mull over the range $4,000$ — 200 cm^{-1} and the spectra of α, α' -dipyridyl

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Since our completing and communicating this paper, a synthetic study of $[\text{CuX}_2(\text{o-phen})]$ (where $\text{X} = \text{Cl}, \text{Br}, \text{I}, \text{NO}_3, \text{SCN}, \frac{1}{2} \text{S}_2\text{O}_3$). P. Spacu, M. Brezeanar, F. Zalaru, *Chem. Abstr.* 1968, **68, 45767) has appeared.

1. R. L. Dutta, D. De and A. Syamal (in part), *This Journal*, 1968, **45**, 663.
2. C. M. Harris, T. N. Lockyer and H. Waterman, *Nature*, 1961, **192**, 424.
3. A. A. Schilt and K. Fritsch, *J. Inorg. Nucl. Chem.*, 1966, **28**, 2678.

has been taken into account from already published sources^{4,5}. For M—NCS the range of CN stretch appears to be 2,040—2,080 cm^{-1} and for M—SCN about 2,080—2,120 cm^{-1} and for bridging group the range is rather broad and around 2,100 cm^{-1} and above^{6,7}. Our complex shows two strong split bands at 2,065 cm^{-1} and 2,100 cm^{-1} in the CN stretching region, thereby confirming the presence of N— bonding in the complex. Over this region α , α' -dipyridyl fortunately has no infrared absorption. The CN—stretching frequency may also be taken to be weakly indicative of bridging thiocyanate. A CS—stretching frequency at 770 cm^{-1} is also in agreement with N— bonding. The neighbouring α , α' -dipyridyl bands are reported to occur at 751 cm^{-1} (strong) and at 890 cm^{-1} (very weak)⁵.

The electronic absorption spectra of the complex as diffuse reflectance indicates two bands around 410—420 $\text{m}\mu$ (24,390—23,810 cm^{-1} and at 720—750 $\text{m}\mu$ (13,890—13,330 cm^{-1}) the last one showing some shoulder to the higher energy side. The spectra recorded upto 1,200 $\text{m}\mu$ does not reveal any other band. In general copper(II) complexes in tetrahedral, planar or octahedral coordination should exhibit ideally three absorption bands⁸. However, commonly this is very seldom observed and mostly broad, asymmetric bands hiding a second band is observed. The present compound does not exhibit any absorption band in the characteristic, low frequency region (8,000–11,000 cm^{-1}) of tetrahedral or distorted tetrahedral copper(II) complexes^{9,10}. Instead, the low frequency band (11,100 cm^{-1}) of the distorted tetrahedral complex, tetrakis(isothiocyanato)copper(II)¹¹, has moved over to 13,890–13,330 cm^{-1} on replacement of two isothiocyanato groups by the strong field α , α' dipyridyl. The infrared indication of the presence of terminal and possibly of weakly bridging isothiocyanate groups together with electronic spectra suggest a distorted planar or distorted octahedral stereochemistry. The dimethylsulfoxide spectra show bands at 27,030—26,320 cm^{-1} and at 14,490—14,080 cm^{-1} indicating lower distortion in DMSO solution than in the solid state. This variation in the extent of distortion appears to be in conformity with the lower disposition of DMSO compared to thiocyanate ion in the spectrochemical series¹². The dimethylsulfoxide (DMSO) spectra, run for all these remaining complexes show absorption region over the ranges 14,490—13,510 cm^{-1} (cf. Table I and Fig. 1).

Complex [Cu(AA) (NO₂)₂] (AA = α , α' -dipyridyl): The NO₂—group is known to give rise to three behaviours: Linking through N(nitro), linking through oxygen (nitrito) and bridging nitro groups. On coordination via nitrogen the frequencies of $\nu_{\text{as}}(\text{NO}_2)$ and $\nu_{\text{s}}(\text{NO}_2)$ are generally raised from the nitrite ion values of $\sim 1,328$ cm^{-1} and 1,260 cm^{-1} towards the values observed for perfectly covalent nitrogroups, 1,586 cm^{-1} and 1,377 cm^{-1} as in nitromethane¹³. Coordination via oxygen generally raises the $\nu_{\text{as}}(\text{NO}_2)$

4. P. C. H. Mitchell, *J. Inorg. Nucl. Chem.*, 1963, **25**, 963.
5. J. R. Ferraro and W. R. Walker, *Inorg. Chem.*, 1965, **4**, 1382.
6. P. C. H. Mitchell and R. J. P. Williams, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1960, 1912.
7. (a) J. Lewis, R. S. Nyholm and P. W. Smith, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1961, 4590.
(b) D. M. L. Goodgame and L. M. Venanzi, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1963, 623.
8. A. F. Cotton and G. Wilkinson, "Advanced Inorganic Chemistry", Interscience Publishers, 1962, p. 753.
9. L. Sacconi and M. Ciampolini, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1964, 278.
10. M. Goodgame and L. I. B. Haines, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1966, (A), 174.
11. D. Forster and D. M. L. Goodgame, *Inorg. Chem.*, 1965, **4**, 823.
12. R. S. Drago, "Physical Method of Inorganic Chemistry", Reinhold Publishing Corporation, New York, 1965.
13. D. C. Smith, C. Y. Pan and J. R. Nielsen, *J. Chem. Phys.*, 1950, **18**, 706.

but lowers $\nu_s(\text{NO}_2)^{14}$. The above complex shows sharp absorption bands at $1,310\text{ cm}^{-1}$, $1,320\text{ cm}^{-1}$ and at $1,370\text{ cm}^{-1}$. The position and number of the bands indicate coordination

Fig. 1. Absorption spectra of mixed ligand complexes in different media.

- (1) $[\text{Cu}(\text{dipy})(\text{NO}_2)_2]$, 0.004M in DMSO
 - (2) $[\text{Cu}(\text{dipy})(\text{NCS})_2]$, 0.004M in DMSO
 - (3) $[\text{Cu}(\text{dipy})(\text{NO}_2)_2]$ diffuse reflectance spectra
 - (4) $[\text{Cu}(\text{dipy})(\text{NCS})_2]$ diffuse reflectance spectra
 - (5) $[\text{Cu}(\text{dipy})(\text{N}_3)_2]$, 0.001M in DMSO
- Optical density scale for (3) and (4) is arbitrary.

through nitrogen as also their *cis*-disposition in the complex. Fortunately again the nearest α, α' -dipyridyl absorption bands occur at $1,270\text{ cm}^{-1}$ (very weak) and $1,415\text{ cm}^{-1}$ (strong) but Nujol absorbs $\sim 1,370\text{ cm}^{-1}$. It may be mentioned in this context that absorption bands at $1,485\text{ cm}^{-1}$ and $1,183\text{ cm}^{-1}$ have been taken to indicate bridging¹⁵

nitro groups in the compound $\left[(\text{NH}_3)_4 \text{CO} \begin{array}{c} \text{NO}_2 \\ \diagdown \quad \diagup \\ \text{N} \\ \diagup \quad \diagdown \\ \text{NH}_2 \end{array} \text{CO} (\text{NH}_3)_4 \right] \text{Cl}_4 \cdot \text{H}_2\text{O}$. However,

the present complex also has bands at $1,150\text{ cm}^{-1}$, $1,450\text{ cm}^{-1}$ and at $1,490\text{ cm}^{-1}$. Neither the $1,490\text{ cm}^{-1}$ band nor the $1,150\text{ cm}^{-1}$ band appears in α, α' -dipyridyl itself but nujol has band at $1,460\text{ cm}^{-1}$. Thus we feel that the infrared spectra provide evidence both for terminal and bridging nitro groups. A comparison of the diffuse reflectance spectra of the nitro complex with that of the isothiocyanato complex reveals a very great shifting in the absorption band from $13,300$ — $13,900\text{ cm}^{-1}$ in the isothiocyanate to $15,620$ — $16,670\text{ cm}^{-1}$ in the nitro complex and is certainly due to a strong-field character of NO_2 -group compared to NCS in the spectrochemical series¹⁶. This shifting to the higher frequency is also an evidence in favour of the NO_2 -group being linked to copper through nitrogen. For, the nitrito group (ONO) has only a weak ligand field character and is placed closed to NCS in the spectrochemical series¹⁷. The

14. (a) P. Tarte, *J. Chem. Phys.*, 1952, **20**, 1572.

(b) D. M. L. Goodgame and M. A. Hitchman, *Inorg. Chem.*, 1964, **3**, 1389.

15. J. Chatt, L. A. Duncanson, B. M. Gatehouse, J. Lewis, R. S. Nyholm, M. L. Tobc, P. F. Todd and M. L. Venanzi, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1959, 4073.

16. Reference 8, p. 579.

17. C. K. Jorgensen, "Absorption and Chemical Bonding in Complexes", Pergamon Press, 1962, p. 109.

absence of any absorption band over the low frequency range (8,000—11,000 cm^{-1}) militates against a tetrahedral or even a distorted tetrahedral stereochemistry^{9,10}. The complex being soluble in DMSO offered us a scope to look into the extent of distortion in such solvent. The absorption bands at 27,030—26,320 cm^{-1} and at 15,380—14,490 cm^{-1} indicating a distortion arising out of weaker dimethylsulphoxide coordination in solution. As for other complexes we have studied only the DMSO spectra and believe that at least in this donor solvent the complexes are distorted octahedral. All of these furnish absorption bands in the range 15,150—14,080 cm^{-1} (cf. Table 1).

Complex [Cu(AA) (N₃)₂]: For this group of complexes we have only the DMSO spectra to discuss. Most of these provide two absorption bands in the visible range although the ones at higher frequency (25,000 cm^{-1}) have a high extinction coefficient. However, the low frequency range over 15,380—14,710 cm^{-1} and as discussed earlier these are believed to be distorted octahedral at least in solution.

The magnetic moments of all the complexes have been evaluated at room temperature and these offered values around 1.7—1.9 B.M. (cf. Table 1). Since much reliance cannot be placed on room temp. magnetic moments for evaluation of stereochemistry¹⁸, the present values lend some support for planar or distorted octahedral structures than for tetrahedral structures.

TABLE I

The Magnetic Moment Values and Absorption Spectral Data of the Mixed Complexes.

Complex	Magnetic Moment			Diffuse reflectance	Absorption Spectral Data (cm^{-1})	
	Dia. Corr. $\times 10^6$	χM (Corr.) $\times 10^6$	μ_{eff} B.M. (T°abs)		DMSO	ϵ_{max}
1. [Cu (dipy) (NCS) ₂]	145	1221	1.74 B.M. (308°)*	13,890—13,330	(i) 27,030—26,320 (ii) 14,490—14,080	858 84.0
2. [Cu (dipy) (NO ₂) ₂]	117	1386	1.85 (308°)	16,670—15,620	(i) 27,030—26,320 (ii) 15,380—14,490	1,090 92.5
3. [Cu (dipy) (N ₃) ₂]	126	1259	1.77 (309°)		(i) 25,000 (ii) 15,380—14,930	2,500 240
4. [Cu (o-phen) (NCS) ₂]	149	1225	1.74 (305.5°)		(i) 27,030—26,320 (ii) 14,490—14,080	704 76.5
5. [Cu (o-phen) (NO ₂) ₂]	120	1194	1.72 (306°)		(i) 26,320 (ii) 14,930—14,290	990 90.0
6. [Cu (o-phen) (N ₃) ₂]	125	1391	1.85 (305.5°)		(i) 25,000 (ii) 15,380—14,710	3,214 270
7. [Cu (nitrophen) (NCS) ₂]	172	1320	1.80 (305.)		(i) — (ii) 14,290—13,700	— 73.5
8. [Cu (nitrophen) (NO ₂) ₂]	143	1348	1.82 (306°)		(i) 24,390 (ii) 15,150—14,080	776 96.0
9. [Cu (nitrophen) (N ₃) ₂]	152	1473	1.90 (305°)		(i) 25,000 (ii) 15,380—14,710	2,336 200

* Figures in parentheses indicate the temp. at which measurements were made.

μ_{eff} was calculated from the relation $\mu_{\text{eff}} = 2.84 (\chi\text{M} (\text{Corr.}) \times \text{T})^{\frac{1}{2}}$ B. M. where T is the absolute temp.

18. J. Lewis and R. A. Walton, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1966, (A), 1559.

EXPERIMENTAL

Two general methods were used for the syntheses of the complexes. $[\text{Cu}(\text{dipy})(\text{BigH})]\text{Cl}_2$, $[\text{Cu}(\text{o-phen})(\text{BigH})]\text{Cl}_2$ and $[\text{Cu}(\text{nitrophen})(\text{BigH})]\text{Cl}_2$ were obtained as described¹ in part I.

(1) *Diisothiocyanato*(α , α' -*dipyridyl*)*copper*(II) : *Method A* : $[\text{Cu}(\text{dipy})(\text{BigH})]\text{Cl}_2$ was dissolved in water and treated slowly under stirring with a dilute solution of NH_4SCN . Bright green crystals separated immediately. These were digested on the steam bath, filtered, washed with water and alcohol and dried in air.

Method B : $\text{CuCl}_2 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$ (0.17 g) was dissolved in water (2—3 ml.) and was treated with an alcoholic solution of α , α' -dipyridyl (0.15 g in 2—3 ml.). A green precipitate formed and was dissolved out by the addition of ~ 15 ml. of warm water. The clear light blue solution was treated slowly with a dilute solution of NH_4SCN with stirring. Bright green crystals separated immediately. These were digested on the steam bath for 30 mins., filtered, washed with water and alcohol and dried in air.

(2) *Diazido*(α , α' -*dipyridyl*)*copper*(II) : This was prepared by following procedures similar to the corresponding diisothiocyanato complex using a dilute solution of NaN_3 instead of NH_4SCN . This is yellowish green in colour.

(3) *Dinitro*(α , α' -*dipyridyl*)*copper*(II) : *Method A*. Biguanide acid sulphate (0.45 g) was dissolved in hot water (~ 10 ml.) and treated with a dil. acetic acid solution of barium hydroxide (0.78 g in ~ 5 ml.). The mixture was digested on steam bath for 30 mins., filtered and the filtrate was treated with copper(II) acetate solution (0.40 g in 7—10 ml. water + 1 ml. dil. acetic acid). The pH of the solution was raised to 6—6.5 by adding dilute NH_4OH . The blue solution thus formed was treated with rect. spirit solution of α , α' -dipyridyl (0.3 g in 5 ml.). This solution was then concentrated to half its volume. The complex α , α' -dipyridyl-biguanide copper(II) acetate solution thus formed was treated slowly under stirring with a dilute solution of NaNO_2 . Fine needles of deep green crystals separated. After allowing it to stand for half an hour at ordinary temperature, these were filtered, washed with cold water, and alcohol and dried in air. The substance is sparingly soluble in hot water.

Method B : This method is like the corresponding diisothiocyanato complex using a dilute solution of NaNO_2 instead of NH_4SCN . Details of methods of syntheses and analyses appear in Table II.

Analytical Procedures : Copper was first precipitated as CuS with H_2S . This precipitate was then dissolved in nitric acid-sulfuric acid mixture and copper was estimated iodometrically. 5-Nitro-o-phenanthroline copper(II) complexes decomposed only incompletely with H_2S . These were ultimately fused with KHSO_4 (10—15 times by weight). The cooled fused mass was then moistened with conc. H_2SO_4 and heated to dense white fumes. This process was repeated for 3-4 times and finally heated strongly for half an hour. The cooled mass was then dissolved in hot acidified (H_2SO_4) water and copper content was estimated iodometrically.

TABLE II

Elemental Analyses of Complexes.

Complex	Method of synthesis	Colour	Copper%		Analysis Nitrogen%		Thiocyanate%	
			Found	Reqd.	Found	Reqd.	Found	Reqd.
1. [Cu (dipy) (NCS) ₂]	A	Bright green	19.10	18.94	16.80	16.69	34.51	34.58
	B	—do—	19.06	18.94	16.74	16.69	34.54	34.58
2. [Cu (dipy) (NO ₂) ₂]	A	Deep green	20.41	20.39	18.20	17.98		
	B	-do-	20.43	20.39	18.00	17.98		
3. [Cu (dipy) (N ₃) ₂]	A	Yellowish green	21.10	20.93				
	B	-do-	21.04	20.93				
4. [Cu (o-phen) (NCS) ₂]	A	Bright green	17.70	17.68	*15.60	15.58	32.30	32.27
	B	-do-	17.69	17.68	15.62	15.58	32.31	32.27
5. [Cu (o-phen) (NO ₂) ₂]	A	Shining deep green	19.05	18.94	16.72	16.69		
	B	-do-	19.00	18.94	16.74	16.69		
6. [Cu (o-phen) (N ₃) ₂]	A	Green with	19.43	19.40				
	B	yellow tinge -do-	19.46	19.40				
7. [Cu(nitrophen) (NCS) ₂]	A	Yellowish green	15.75	15.71	17.35	17.31	28.70	28.68
	B	-do-	15.73	15.71	17.36	17.31	28.72	28.68
8. [Cu(nitrophen) (NO ₂) ₂]	A	Light green	16.72	16.69	18.41	18.39		
	B	-do-	16.75	16.69	18.40	18.39		
9. [Cu (nitrophen) (N ₃) ₂]	A	Greenish yellow	16.93	17.06				
	B	-do-	16.90	17.06				

Thiocyanate was estimated as silver thiocyanate.

Nitrogen was estimated by semimicro combustion technique (Dumas' method).

The magnetic moment values of the complexes at room temperature were measured by a Gouy's Balance with field strength 3.366×10^3 gauss, using G. R. grade copper(II) sulfate pentahydrate as a standard. Diamagnetic corrections were taken from Selwood.¹⁹ The absorption spectral data in solid and in dimethylsulfoxide solution appear in Table I. The IR spectra were run as Nujol mull.

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